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PROJECT

INNORATE

Data-driven tools for supporting and improving
the decision-making processes of investors for financing innovative SMEs

D1.1: State-of-play in innovative technology assessment and rating

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Main authors

- Mr. Stefano Carosio, Mr. Alessandro Mistretta, Ms. Alessandra Zulian, Mr. Alberto Da Re (Unismart Padova Enterprise)

Reviewers

- Ms Anastasia Matonaki, Mr. Kostas Giagtzoglou, Mr. Kostas Chisiridis (Q-PLAN)
- Ms. Giulia Zendron, Mr. Ioannis Kostopoulos (White Research)
- Dr. Bongryul You, Dr. Youngsoo Kim, Dr. Hyungseung Yi, Dr. Yushin Kim (KOTEC)

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASI	Italian Space Agency
CRA	Credit Rating Agency
DWPI	Derwent World Patents Index
DPCI	Derwent Patent Citations Index
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
KTRS	KOTEC Technology Rating System
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
NPV	Net Present Value
ROA	Real Options Approach
ROK	Republic of Korea
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
S&P	Standard and Poor's Corporation

Executive summary

Objectives

This document describes the work and the outcomes of Task 1.1, which aim at describing the current state-of-play of technology assessment. In particular, the interest is in different methodologies, tools and services used for assessing and rating technologies of innovative SMEs. Besides the traditional approaches used by investors and financial institutions in general, such as banks, VCs, etc., the main focus was on revealing what new ways for technology assessment have been developed and used by other players involved in this topic. A comparative analysis of the identified practices will be performed at the end, in order to extract meaningful insights regarding good practices, pros and cons, as well as challenges and gaps within the current state-of-play.

Approach

The study was conducted through desk research, focusing on online sources, companies' websites and available material, but also through material and information sent by partners and asked directly to the most interesting players in the sector. Many information and data collected were sensitive or proprietary, thus it was not possible to incorporate them in the report. Whenever necessary, direct interviews were conducted to better understand the company's methodology or approach.

After a brief introduction, in Chapter 2 a portrayal of the evolution of technology assessment during the years is presented. Starting from the well-known financial assessment, later studies and researches started to develop different ways to measure the technological value. In recent years, there has been some interest also in developing a systematic approach to examine the validity itself of technology evaluation models and improve them. In Chapter 3 a review of the main methodologies and tools to evaluate innovative technology is discussed. At the end, additional recent interesting methods were considered and described: methods involving predictive or artificial intelligence, the patent landscape analysis, or the use of social metrics through big data analysis. Examples and breakdowns of the most interesting case studies have been described in Chapter 4. Then, in Chapter 5 an overall analysis can be found, in order to highlight meaningful aspects emerged from this study, such as pros and cons emerged in the previous sections, interesting new approaches and challenges and gaps that still need to be filled. Finally, in Chapter 6 it is presented a first preliminary evaluation of the project's idea, analyzing the results coming from the event "Innovation Talks", organized by Unismart in collaboration with the University of Padua, that took place on the 18th of March 2019. Since more than 300 stakeholders (entrepreneurs, investors and innovators) attended the event, a short questionnaire was provided to gather useful insights.

Results

What emerged from this study is that different methodologies can mainly be distinguished depending on what they evaluate (i.e. financial or technological aspects) and how they perform the evaluation (i.e. through qualitative interviews with experts or using mathematical or scoring model producing a quantitative result). The most successful assessment method has proved to be constituted by multi-dimensional scoring sheets or rating processes. Some additional interesting features were recognized, and could be worth further investigation. Also, preliminary insights with stakeholders (through interviews conducted during the study, as well as thanks to the event organized by Unismart) have revealed to provide extremely useful feedbacks on technology assessment.

1. Introduction

Innovation is the key factor to competitiveness in the present economy. However, in the European landscape finance still has difficulties reaching innovative SMEs, due to the current incapacity of investors and lenders (e.g. banks, business angels, VCs, etc.) to appropriately assess disruptive and potentially market creating innovations. In fact, to correctly assess these innovations, one cannot overlook a correct assessment of the inherent technology. Thus, a deep technology and market expertise is essential, but investors and lenders often lack this knowledge. The result is an information asymmetry, which intensifies the risk aversion of investors, that have difficulties assessing the real technology potential. The only aspect that is taken into account turns to be the financial one, but this is by definition inadequate for innovative companies, which often have a lack of historical financial information. The outcome is that the lack of a tool for obtaining sufficient and high-quality information on innovative technology SMEs creates a severe bottleneck inhibiting lending and financial investments.

Given these premises, it becomes evident that there is a need for a new tool for technology assessment and rating, that can support and incentivize the decision-making process of investors and lenders. This tool should look beyond the financial aspect and past history of SMEs, and rather emphasize on their market and technological potential. Hence, in order to develop such a tool, a state-of-paly analysis of existing technology assessment and rating methodologies, tools and services for prioritizing and selecting high growth potential SMEs should be done. A comparison between current methods is essential to grasp pros and cons of each one of them, as well as best practices and challenges and gaps to be filled. Furthermore, from this study new interesting and promising approaches could arise, and they could be integrated and implemented in the new assessment tool.

This will be the starting point for future tasks, setting the base of information for the co-creation workshop with users and stakeholders, as well as for the next design and development of InnoRate's innovative assessment methodology and platform.

Figure 1: Conceptual graph with main figures involved with technology rating systems

2. Background of technology assessment

A brief portrayal of the evolution of technology assessment during the years is presented in this section, from the first researches until the latest ones. In fact, as the need for a reliable technology evaluation method increased due to the shift in the market, extensive researches on metrics and ratings were performed.

Since the early 1960s, technology assessment has received consistent attention from both academia and industry. At first, also due to the history of the well-established credit evaluation system, financial measures were considered, such as net present value (NPV) and internal rate of return (IRR), as well as different complex option models. The problem with this kind of assessment is that it is based on the past financial history of the company, a set of information that is not always available and that does not comprehend the disruptive potential intrinsic in the innovative business.

Then, to better evaluate the technological aspects and their potential, technological measures (e.g. patents and technology adoption) and market indicators (e.g. life cycle) have been proposed. In 1990 Roure and Keeley suggested three perspectives in evaluating the technologies in a venture: management, environment, and the firm. The management perspective relates to organizational or individual capabilities that make a firm's technology or R&D-related activities effective and efficient. The environment perspective is applied in predicting the successful diffusion of these capabilities in

Figure 2: Historical evolution of assessment methodologies

the market. Finally, the firm perspective regards the advantages of the technology itself as a resource and as a strategic choice for the company itself.

In addition to financial and technological measures, various quantitative and qualitative measures have been proposed. Balachandra and Friar (1997) categorized a large number of factors that determine the success of a technology into four major categories: market, technology, environment, and organization. In 2004, Åstebro studied and examined the impact of 36 innovation, technology and market characteristics on the probability that early stage R&D projects would be successful, and found that the best forecasting of success was determined by factors such as expected profitability, technological opportunity, development risk and appropriability conditions.

Along with the efforts to find success factors for technological and innovative projects, a strong emphasis was put also in developing various evaluation systems for early technology review. Cooper first introduced the Stage-Gate model in 1986 for managing the new product development process. Many Stage-Gate variations with a more technological orientation have been then developed (Eldred and Shapiro, 1996; Eldred and McGrath, 1997; Ajamian and Koen, 2002). In parallel, Product and Cycle-Time Excellence (PACE) has been also widely applied to the successful product development (McGrath, 1996).

Many of the early stage assessments are implemented through some type of multi-dimensional scoring sheet or rating process, whose advantages will be described in Paragraph 3.2.2. The efforts towards the optimization of a technology evaluation model can be divided into two categories: the model development and its implementation and improvement. Park et al. (2010) argue that a majority of the studies tend to concentrate on evaluation model development, but not enough studies have on their focus the improvement of the evaluation model itself. In 2018, a study from Noh et al. recognized this research gap and tried to develop a systematic approach to examine the validity of technology evaluation models and improve them. Three criteria were considered: 1) the coherence of the evaluation results with the evaluation purpose, 2) the appropriateness of the evaluation methods, and 3) the concreteness of the evaluation model.

3. Analysis of methodologies

In this section, a review of the main methodologies and tools to evaluate innovative technology is presented. The aim of this chapter is to give an idea of the main instruments that have been developed in order to perform technology assessment. Their implementation by different players will then be described in Chapter 4.

To recap the existing approaches to technology evaluation, two basic elements can be considered as the core of an evaluation model:

1. what to evaluate;
2. how to evaluate.

The former, “what to evaluate”, refers to the evaluation target. As previously described in Chapter 2, while initially the aspects under measure were essentially the financial ones, further studies in the sector brought more attention also on the technological measures. Key technology evaluation areas include not only technological features, but also technology-based organizational capabilities and technological impacts on markets, since all these factors work together to determine the value of a technology.

The latter, “how to evaluate”, is connected to evaluation methods, which can in turn be largely classified as qualitative, quantitative, or a combination of both. Qualitative methods have the advantage of capturing all the softer aspects of technology-related factors. They include interviews with experts, or a focus group study. On the contrary, quantitative approaches offer hard data and provide numerical explication. Such inherent advantages make them attractive for use in technology evaluation. Numerous methodologies have been utilized as quantitative approaches, including complex mathematical models, scoring models based on multi-criteria decision-making analyses, and heuristic algorithms. Finally, a simultaneous use of both qualitative and quantitative methods has also been attempted, in what is generally called a “qualitative hybrid/mixed” approach.

3.1 What to evaluate

Starting from financial evaluation, being the most commonly used by investors and lenders for decision making, during the last decades technology evaluation has seen a strong development, also due to technology increasing disruptive potential.

3.1.1 Finance

Assessing the financial aspect of a SME essentially means measuring its default risk. This type of evaluation is necessary in order to secure stability of fund, which is essential to prevent depletion of the source of fund and enable sustainable financial support. If only the growth potential of a firm is examined, there is a risk of underestimating the negative aspects, in particular the risk of insolvency from the enterprise.

This risk level is based on the company's commercialization risk, as well as on external risks such as economic cycle, etc. In other word, it is the combination of business risk evaluation results and environment risk evaluation results. It is tied on the company's past history, since it is based on past financial records and business stability.

A commonly used business measure is represented by Net Present Value, which is the difference between the present value of cash inflows and the present value of cash outflows over a period of time. It is assumed that an investment with a positive NPV will be profitable, while an investment with a negative NPV is considered risky. Finding the discount rate that results in an NPV equal to zero gives the Internal Rate of Return. The lower IRR, the higher the associated risk is.

Environment variables can be divided in external environment variables and internal environment variables. The former regard all the outside factors or influences that impact the operation of business, such as industrial production, leading indicators, operating rate, earnings credit rate, currency exchange rate, etc. The latter instead is related to elements within the organization, like number of employees, year of establishment, business category, age of the representative, etc.

3.1.2 Technology

Another key aspect to be measured, which is getting more and more relevant, is the technological one. Since its potentially disruptive outcomes, its role in evaluating the value of a technological SME is nowadays of extreme importance, and cannot be neglected. In fact, technological innovation is acknowledged as the ultimate source of competitive advantage for firms, and also as the most important driver of economic and social development for nations. Hence, technology assessment has an increasingly critical role, both for companies as well as for private and public institutions, and unlike the financial assessment, this is a measure of the future growth potential of the company.

It can be defined in many different ways, depending on the specific context, but one relevant definition taken from the U.S. Office of Technology Assessment (1972) is:

“[...] a form of policy research which provides a balanced appraisal to the policy makers. Ideally, it is a system to ask the right questions and obtain correct and timely answers. It identifies policy issues, assesses the impact of alternative courses of action and presents findings. It is a method of analysis that systematically appraises the nature, significance, status, and merit of a technological program”.

It can be defined as a form of policy research that examines short- and long-term consequences (e.g. societal, economic, ethical, legal) of the application of a technology. The goal is to provide policy makers with information on policy alternatives.

In many assessment methodologies, technology evaluation is divided in four major categories:

1. technology;
2. management capability;
3. marketability;
4. business feasibility.

Technology refers to the application of scientific knowledge for practical purposes, especially in industry. As defined by the IPCC, technology is “[...] the practical application of knowledge to achieve particular task that employs both technical artefacts (hardware, equipment) and (social) information (software, know-how for production and use of artefacts)”. As the specific nature of technology depends on the tasks to be achieved, the technology definition is different depending on the context of application. With regards to technology assessment, it concerns aspects such as the value of the technology and its superiority with respect to the landscape, as well as the degree of technological innovation, its stage of development, position in technological life-cycle, etc.

Management capability indicates the general skills with which managers construct, integrate, and reconfigure the organization’s resources and assets. These capabilities enable top management teams to face the environment, improve organizational performance, and maintain and create competitive advantages. Also, designing organizational and strategic processes, managers lead the company to innovate and grow, driving new product development and establishing external relationships with customers and suppliers at the advantage of the organization. Overall, management capabilities are composed of the human, technical, and conceptual resources of their top managers.

Marketability is a measure of whether a product will appeal to buyers and sell at a certain price range to generate a profit. It depends on the competitive position of the technology, product or service with respect to a market. In other words, it represents the potential that a product will sell. Factors involving the target market (size, readiness, etc.) as well as competitors’ presence and characteristics are to be considered.

Business feasibility refers to the viability of an idea, a new business or a product. The goal of a feasibility study is to assess the requirements for the realization of the business and determine, after having considered all the significant factors, if the company is able to fulfill them. The factors comprehend problems and opportunities, a determination of the successful outcomes and range of costs and benefits of different solutions, as well as a cost benefit analysis of the actual business viability.

3.2 How to evaluate

Apart from the object of evaluation, assessment methodologies can be divided based on the way they are implemented and the results they yield. Different evaluation models can be largely classified as qualitative or quantitative.

3.2.1 Qualitative

Qualitative assessment is focused on understanding how people make meaning of and experience their environment or world. Different from quantitative approach, qualitative approach employs sector expert as the primary means of data collection (e.g. interviews, focus groups, etc.).

Interviews comprise a number of generally open-ended questions that yield information exploiting people's experiences, perceptions, opinions, feelings, and knowledge. It is common to engage in face-to-face or virtual verbal interviews. However, interviews may also be conducted with a group or through questionnaires.

Qualitative approaches have the advantage of capturing softer aspects that are canceled out in more schematic quantitative approaches. Also, they leverage the experiences and knowledge of experts in the sectors, and the feeling that they have developed during the years. When conducted directly, they also have the advantage of creating a relation with the participants, thus improving access to information, providing meaning to results, and taking into account the background behind the figures being evaluated.

On the other hand, qualitative assessments require skills and experience to undertake, and furthermore results could be questioned in terms of subjectivity (this could be solved through cross-checking).

3.2.2 Quantitative

On the contrary, quantitative methods use numbers for interpreting data, and focus on scores, measurements, defined outcomes. This leads to more comparable results, and a fast identification of the most promising technologies can be performed by investors. The downside is that useful experts' insights could be missed.

Numerous methodologies have been utilized as quantitative approaches: on one side complex mathematical models, and on the other side scoring models based on multi-criteria decision analyses (MCDA).

Mathematical models

Several mathematical models have been developed especially as a tool for real options approaches (ROA). This has received great attention in the last decade, since an initial investment in an innovative project is similar to the purchase of an option on a future investment. If the project found success, then it creates the option to make a significantly larger investment with relatively higher expected benefit. Otherwise, if the project fails to reach success, then there is no need to commit any further resources, and therefore the downside risk is limited to the initial investment cost.

Generally, the real options model assumes that there are $T + 1$ reviews stages ($t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T$), i.e. the milestones in the firm's project. The stage t is characterized by the expected product performance $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, where x_k is the individual performance. From state X_i , after decision d , the system moves to a new state X_j at stage $t + 1$ with transition probability $p_{ij}^t(d)$. Then, for example, the market demand $S(t)$ during stage $t \in [T + 1, L]$ could be estimated as:

$$S(t) = \underbrace{\alpha F(X_T)[m - N(t - 1)]}_{\text{innovation demand}} + \underbrace{\frac{\beta}{m} N(t - 1)[m - N(t - 1)]}_{\text{imitation demand}} + \underbrace{\gamma N(t - 1)}_{\text{repeat purchase}}$$

where $F(X_T)$ represents the probability that X_T exceeds the market requirement, m is the total market size, $N(t)$ is the market demand through stage t , α the coefficient of innovation, β the coefficient of imitation, and γ the average product consumption. The first term represents the estimated innovation demand on the market, the second term the imitation demand, whereas the last term indicates the estimated repeat purchase. Parameters α , β , and γ can be estimated by analogous products or by statistical methods if initial sales data is available.

However, although numerous research and studies have been done to develop many different mathematical models, they are not commonly used because of the diversity of project types, resources and criteria used.

Scoring models

Since a scoring model produces final evaluation results simply by adding a set of different factors, it is one of the most commonly used in technology assessment. Individual methods may be different from one another in term of specific factors and indicators which are used, but the procedure and the result are similar.

The general approach is to use a scorecard to review various attributes, that include not only the characteristics of the technology itself, but also the characteristics of the firm. Usually, different declination of the following characteristics can be found as technology evaluation factors: level of technology, management capability, marketability and profitability of technology. Nonetheless, different declinations are to be found, and some models may only use some of them. For each attribute, a 5 or 10-point score is given by an expert (or a committee of experts), and then a final score is obtained by simply summing the score of each attribute, for a maximum of 100 points.

Each attribute used has its own evaluation criteria. For example, a “knowledge management” attribute can be evaluated in terms of the length of service of the manager, as well as his educational background. Whereas, a “output of technology development” attribute could be evaluated based on the number of patents, technology certifications, the number of R&D projects in the last 3 years, etc. At the same time, “market potential” is evaluated in terms of the expected market size, the growth potential of market, and the prospects for the economy, etc. It is evident that some attributes’ criteria are relatively objective, whereas others are relatively subjective. Thus, especially for the latter, the knowledge and experience of an expert is fundamental.

Figure 3: Example of technology evaluation factors and attributes (Sohn et al., 2005)

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Attributes</i>	<i>Score</i>
Management	Knowledge management	5
	Technology experience	5
	Management ability	5
	Fund-raising ability	5
	Human resource	5
Technology	Environment of technology development	5
	Output of technology development (eg patents, certifications)	5
	Success in new technology development projects	5
	Technology superiority	10
	Technology commercialization	10
Marketability	Market potential	5
	Market characteristics and competitions	5
	Product competitiveness	10
Profitability	Feasibility of sales plan	10
	Feasibility of business implementation schedule (new*)	5
	Ratio of ordinary income to sales (old ⁺)	
	Expected return on investment (new*)	5
	Profit forecasts (old ⁺)	

New*: For companies less than 3 years old. Old⁺: For companies older than 3 years.

However, most banks and technology financial institutions prefer to use a rating system, the standard ones involving rating starting from AAA (the highest) followed by AA, A, B, etc. The use of a rating approach has several advantages over 1-100 scoring. First of all, evaluation results presented as a rating category are convenient for users to identify credit quality. Second, it is possible to develop differentiated strategies for different categories. Third, it is easier to compare and combine rating results coming from different evaluation models. Fourth, according to the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, banking institutions need to base the capital requirement on their own internal rating systems and use external rating systems.

To pass from a 1-100 numerical score to the standard rating system, simple intervals could be used, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Simple criteria of technology rating.

	<i>Rating</i>									
	<i>AAA</i>	<i>AA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>BBB</i>	<i>BB</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>CCC</i>	<i>CC</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>
Interval (points)	Above 90	85 ~ 89	80 ~ 84	75 ~ 79	70 ~ 74	65 ~ 69	60 ~ 64	55 ~ 59	50 ~ 54	Below 50

However, it was found that this approach is not the best one, since it leads to an abnormal distribution of default rates for different ratings, as can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Default rate of each rating using simple intervals (Moon et al., 2011)

To resolve this problem, Sohn et al. (2005) proposed to use a logistic regression model. Eight factors extracted from the factor analysis of 16 technology attributes (Figure 3) were used as input variables, and a default indicator (1 = default, 0 = non-default) was used as target variable. In this process, it has to be pointed out that the final score is a relative score, not absolute, since it is derived from the default probability that is very sensitive to both sample size and the ratio of default to non-default. A study in 2011 proposed a rating system to categorize the companies according to the technology score based on the criteria of frequency distribution and default rate for each rating category. In terms of frequency distribution, companies in the 10 category groups (AAA to D) should be distributed following a normal distribution, centered on the middle ratings (BB and B). In terms of default rate instead, the ratio of companies defaulted in each group must decrease from D to AAA, being close to zero at AA and AAA. The best interval boundaries were empirically found, ensuring that the frequency distribution looks like a normal distribution and also that the default rates keep decreasing from lower to higher rating category. Figure 6 from Moon et al., 2011, shows the results obtained with this method.

Figure 6: Rating results based on distribution ration and default rate (Moon et al., 2011)

3.3 Additional aspects

In recent years, some additional aspects were considered and implemented to extend assessment processes. Thanks to the development of technologies (e.g. Artificial Intelligence and Big Data analytics tools) and due to the increasing importance of different market and advertising platforms (like social media), the assessment landscape has seen the appearance of new tools and metrics.

3.3.1 Predictive Intelligence

Nowadays companies have access to more data than ever before. They also have access to better tools to understand and interpret this data. So, companies started to exploit these new opportunities and try to predict market trends, consumer needs, etc. Predictive Intelligence technology works by following a three-step process: analysis, interpretation and response. The technology collects and analyzes the available sets of data. These data are then automatically interpreted by sophisticated algorithms. From this, it's possible to make predictions about emerging trends, market shifts, competitors' presence, etc.

However, for predictive intelligence to be effective in use (and be sensitive to specific needs/uniqueness), it requires very large sample sizes (e.g. 10,000 plus) and separate large hold out samples to justify their selection. The datasets also need to hold high quality, consistent performance metrics. The limiting factor with any predictive analytical approach normally comes down to the prediction being based on solid credible performance criteria.

3.3.2 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence is where technology, systems and software are able to interpret their environment in order to take actions that maximize the chance of successfully achieving goals or outcomes. AI has become highly popular today owing to its useful contribution in collecting and analyzing the amount of data that are accessible. Artificial Intelligence, built upon machine learning which learns over time, offers a more objective tool, with less possibility of mistake and a huge potential of analyzing vast volumes of data. It represents the perfect solution of a system which has the capability to go through thousands of records and come up with a solution.

It should be noted, in terms of predictive modelling, that there are many different approaches and some of these carry greater risks. Measuring thousands of data points and then using machine learning or neural networks in an attempt to predict outcomes can create a “black box approach” to assessment, meaning that illogical or biased variables are used to predict outcomes. The second danger is one of overgeneralization: neural networks, for example, can explore different relationships in large sets of data, and attempt to learn these, but the patterns they detect with large numbers of variables can be illusory, that is, the next set of data doesn’t follow these patterns and the network does not predict success or outcomes.

3.3.3 Patent landscape analysis

Most of technology information contained in patents is not published anywhere else. There are literally tens of millions of published patents and patent application references available for review. Patent landscape analysis, often referred to as “patent mapping”, is a proven multistep process that employs computer software and human intelligence to parse through, organize and extract value from this huge source of information. In a nutshell, patent landscape analysis provides insight into the innovations that underlie technology and products.

A complete patent landscape analysis project consists of a set of technical references and related analytics from which important legal, business and technology information can be extracted. This information enables large corporations, startups, universities, research institutions, and investors to understand and make informed decisions prior to investing time and money into new technology and product development opportunities. Nonetheless, there continues to be a need to find a credible IP valuation approach, particularly for IP that has no specific current income stream attached.

3.3.4 Social metrics

With the shift that is happening in recent years, social media and platform are gaining more and more relevance as a tremendous source of data. Exploiting this data can give useful insights into the success that a product or a firm is collecting, and thus it is a measure of its potential.

The first and easiest social metric to measure is *volume*: the size of the conversation about the firm. This is a great initial indicator of interest, and it is also helpful to track how this change over time (to point out emerging trends for example). Another aspect to be considered is the firm’s *reach*, in other words how big and diverse its audience is. This is a measure of potential market size. One of the most important areas to measure is *engagement*, that is how people are participating in conversations about the firm, spreading the content or engaging with the topic. Finally, another social metric that can be analyzed is the *share of voice*, i.e. how the social presence of the firm compares to competitors.

4. Case studies and most interesting tools, with pros & cons

This chapter presents the most interesting indicative case studies and their assessment process. They were chosen with the intent of trying to cover and offer an example of the different methodologies described in the previous section, and for each case its peculiarities will be highlighted whenever possible. References to other companies and methodologies can be found in Appendix 1. Many information and data are sensitive or proprietary, thus it was not possible to incorporate them in the report, or the company did not consent to share them.

4.1 Korea Technology Finance Corporation – KTRS

The credit guarantee scheme of KOTEC was thought to help innovative SMEs whose access to credit is limited due to lack of collateral capacity, despite their prominent technological competency. It's mainly for this approach that KOTEC's credit guarantee scheme is otherwise called the 'technology guarantee scheme'. It refers to a credit guarantee whose decision is made on the basis of a technology assessment. Through KOTEC's credit guarantee scheme, tech SMEs can overcome the problem of collateral deficiency and obtain financing for their R&D efforts and business operation. KOTEC remains a true partner for innovative SMEs throughout the whole periods of their business life cycle. KOTEC's scheme has performed a leading role for 30 years since its foundation in 1989.

Support to technological competitiveness of SMEs and promotion to the technology finance market in Korea are the two main purposes of the system. Particularly interesting is the methodology developed by KOTEC to measure future values of intangible assets, such as intellectual property rights, patents or other. Talking about the main businesses of KOTEC's reality is possible to underline and organize them in core businesses and additional businesses.

The core ones are:

1. technology guarantee
2. technology evaluation
3. investment linked with guarantee
4. managing right to indemnity

whereas the additional ones can be summed in:

1. guidance for management and technology
2. support for technology innovation

The approach is oriented on a technology evaluation and field investigation instead of a traditional credit evaluation and field evaluation. The tool used in order to reach such operations as technology guarantee or technology evaluation, is KOTEC Technology Rating System (KTRS).

The first aspect KTRS is trying to improve is the "information asymmetry" from the investor to the innovator. In this way the flow of finance from financial institution to normally considered risky SMEs might be considered from another point of view. As already underlined, KTRS approach is focused on technology-based business aspects, trying to re-evaluate, with precise and studied parameters, the financial situation of a company.

KTRS is a technology rating system belonging to the KOTEC scheme, and it is organized in KTRS based models and other policy-oriented models.

There are more than one KTRS based models:

- KTRS – the representative model
- KTRS-SM – for startup business within five years after their establishment
- KTRS-BM – for small size enterprises with the annual amount of KRW 1 billion or less.

KTRS is composed of a total of 65 sub models under 13 categories: three for KTRS based models and ten for policy-oriented models. What changes with the KTRS is the object of evaluation. The focus is pointed at the growth potential in the future of an enterprise, instead of credit risk, probability of insolvency etc. However, the structure of KTRS is thought to evaluate at one side the growth potential, and at the other side the possibility of insolvency. This is done, despite we are talking about a technology assessment system, to secure the stability of fund.

The process of calculating ratings in a technology assessment is composed by:

1. Input step
2. Rating calculating step
3. Rating output step

Figure 7: Process of Rating Calculation in KTRS (courtesy of KOTEC)

The technology evaluation table is organized in four major categories and 33 sub-categories. The categories are: management capability, technology, marketability and business feasibility. For every sub category, an examiner input a grade that could be from A to E according to the criteria of assessment. Environment variables are used as standard variables to check the possibility of insolvency. There are two types of environmental variables: external and internal. The external ones are seven in total: small and medium sized manufacturing industrial production index, leading composite index, average manufacturing industry operation rate index, national credit earning rate, business survey index, and KRW-USD exchange rate. Instead the internal ones are four: number of

regular employees, year of establishment, business category, age of the representative and whether to have own business place.

The second step is the rating calculation. Is here that the future growth potential and the probability of insolvency is assessed. The future potential is measured by calculating a technology business capability grade (through AHP technique), and a business growth potential grade, of a target enterprise, through a statistical technique named “Logit Regression Model”. Also, the business risk is evaluated with the just cited statistical method. On the other side the environment risk is calculated assessing the relation between internal and external variables adding the default cases already occurred.

The output rating is a weighted sum of technology business grades on the growth potential and the risk grades evaluating the probability of insolvency. “The aim is to provide an assessment with a credit rating similar format”. The technology evaluation rating represents the relational grade of business feasibility of a target technology.

Consideration about “European Transferability”

The idea and the project of KOTEC system scheme is obviously appealing for the European context. Undoubtedly adjustments for differences of markets, players, and business environment should be implemented to let the system works properly. Furthermore, the use of the system, as it is in Korea, requires important investments in order to found a technology assessment center with highly qualified staff. The wide pool of stuff available, from which a lot of agencies draw, can be trained and supported for using KTRS.

However, technical issues are also present. KOTEC during the years have accumulated a wide database rich of previous evaluation data and cases studies. The database assumes the implementation of a statistically based risk level calculation. Such a database requires a great amount of time to be built.

In the addressing of such issues in a transferability optic, the set of evaluation indicators needed for the assessment of a company would be implemented in a different environmental risk field and adjusted to the peculiarity of the market. InnoRate project will focus on such an approach.

A key aspect regarding the implementation of such a system is by whom it would be operated. A logic consideration is that it would be important if the assessment would be done in an independent manner from the guarantee issuing organizations. From this point of view, the most feasible way this platform could be implemented in Europe is as a European-wide service, with central funding. Opinions of experts appears as one of the most important features to implement to a KTRS “European mode”.

4.2 Euler Hermes Rating GmbH – TRIBRating

Launched in Germany in June 2017, TRIBRating is a new rating service specifically designed for SMEs and Midcaps, provided by Euler Hermes Rating GmbH, a credit rating agency in the European Union. The credit rating performed by EHRG is expressed by using an established and defined ranking system.

One of the specifications for a regulated credit rating is that it must be communicated on a non-selective basis and in a timely manner. EHRG’s regulated credit ratings are placed on the website and distributed by subscription via EHRG’s Rating Portal. The Credit Rating Agency (CRA) Regulation delineates private credit ratings as credit ratings “produced pursuant to an individual order and provided exclusively to the person who placed the order” that “are not intended for public disclosure or distribution by subscription” and are underling to a responsibility of confidentiality and limitations

on distribution. Customers are not allowed to publish private credit ratings or divulge them by subscription. Clients can use private credit ratings only for internal purposes and, in case, with EHRG's consent, share them with a controlled number of third parties on confidential basis as long as the sharing is alike to public disclosure or distribution by subscription.

Figure 8: Credit rating distinction (courtesy of TRIBRating)

Type	RATING*	
	PUBLIC	PRIVATE
Disclosed on	EHRG website	Rating Portal
Regulation	REGULATED	EXEMPT
Methodology	Regulated methodology	(Regulated) methodology
Monitoring	Mandatory	Optional

Representatives of the rated company, organizations, etc., directly or indirectly send to Euler Hermes Rating GmbH a request to set a credit rating. In this case, the ratings are considered solicited as defined in the CRA Regulation. Credit ratings can also be released without being requested by the rated entity. In this case, the ratings are considered "unsolicited", again by CRA Regulation's definition. Unsolicited credit ratings can sometimes be issued just with the support of publicly available information. EHRG gives a credit rating only if the information base is considered sufficient from a quality point of view and comes from trustworthy sources.

EHRG uses credit rating categories to demonstrate its view on the creditworthiness of the rated entity. The scale starts from AAA (strongest creditworthiness) and arrives to D (default). Rating categories from AAA to CCC are enriched by a plus (+) or minus (-) if necessary, with the aim to show their relative position within the rating category.

Figure 9: EHRG rating categories explanation (courtesy of TRIBRating)

Category	Explanation
AAA	In the opinion of EHRG, AAA rated entities demonstrate an excellent credit quality and the lowest default risk.
AA	In the opinion of EHRG, AA rated entities demonstrate a very high credit quality with a very low default risk.
A	In the opinion of EHRG, A rated entities demonstrate a high credit quality with a low default risk.
BBB	In the opinion of EHRG, BBB rated entities demonstrate a medium credit quality with a moderate default risk.
BB	In the opinion of EHRG, BB rated entities demonstrate a medium-low credit quality with a slightly increased default risk.
B	In the opinion of EHRG, B rated entities demonstrate a low credit quality with an increased default risk.
CCC	In the opinion of EHRG, CCC rated entities demonstrate a very low credit quality with a high default risk.
CC	In the opinion of EHRG, CC rated entities demonstrate a very low credit quality, an event of default is very likely.
C	In the opinion of EHRG, C rated entities demonstrate a very low credit quality, an event of default is imminent.
D / SD	D rated entities have defaulted, as defined by the rating agency. The rated entity is assigned an SD rating (Selective Default) if it has only defaulted on certain debt obligations.
PLUS (+) MINUS (-)	Rating categories from AA to CCC are modified by a PLUS (+) or MINUS (-), where required, in order to show their relative position within the rating category.

In addition to the rating notations, EHRG also publishes a rating outlook that represents EHRG's opinion on the likely direction of the credit rating over the following twelve months. A rating outlook can be placed into one of four categories: positive, negative, stable and direction uncertain.

If new information comes to be useful to lead to an upgrade, downgrade or withdrawal of a credit rating, and thus the rating is consequently put under a specific review, the rating could be placed on a "watch" status for the period of the review. A "watch" status is also performed if the documents and the information requested during the monitoring process are not sent in time and are expected in the near future. In this case, the status is generally of "uncertain". Credit ratings can also be assigned a "current" or "withdrawn" tag. "Withdrawn" means that the rating is no longer provided and does not reflect EHRG's current view.

To assign the credit rating, EHRG methodology follows ten steps:

1. Receipt of documentation and analysis;
2. Site visit or confidence call where applicable;
3. Creation of draft rating report and proposed rating;
4. Rating committee meeting and determination;
5. Submission of credit rating and the rating rationale (draft) to the related entity and, where applicable, the customer;
6. Rated entity points out any factual errors that may have been made and/or inadvertent inclusion of confidential information, if applicable;
7. Possible consideration of comments (another rating committee meeting where applicable);
8. Completion and submission of the credit rating report to the rated entity and the customer where applicable;
9. Public dissemination;
10. Monitoring.

EHRG set up the project team at the start of each credit rating process. With a solicited rating, the customer also assigns a contact person who will be in contact during the rating process. Once the accessible information has been analyzed, the project team prepares the draft report and proposes a rating level. The rating proposal is then presented to the rating committee for the final settlement, using the draft report and any additional descriptions given by the lead analyst and/or other analysts. The rating committee may request extra information. Only the rating committee can assign credit ratings and outlooks. The draft rating report is then sent to the rated entity. The rated subject or its agent must be notified at least 24 hours in advance (within the rated entity's business hours) of the possible publication/dissemination of the rating and its rationale. In this period, the rated entity has the possibility to indicate any factual imprecision and/or accidental inclusion of confidential information to EHRG. At the end of the process, credit rating is published/disseminated along with the rating rationale.

The point is to guarantee that credit ratings are constantly monitored in order to identify any changes that might impact the credit rating/outlook and certify the continued validity of the published rating level. The client is obligated to tell any developments that might impact the credit rating/outlook during the monitoring period. If a credit rating or a rating outlook change during the monitoring process, it will also be communicated to the rated entity or, where possible, customer for comment at least one full business day in advance during business hours.

To go further in details about TRIBRating's methodology, two of the four rating methodologies are now presented. The issuer-level ratings and the issuance-level ratings on corporates. The issuance-level ratings on project finance transactions and the issuance-level ratings on structured finance transaction are not presented, both for brevity and also because they are not very dissimilar from the two presented here.

Issuer rating methodology

The issuer rating methodology is organized into 2 main areas of analysis:

1. Business risk
2. Financial risk

Business risk starts from the information given by the issuer on its internal and external market analysis. The group of analysts working on the rating assessment, thanks to the information given and with some management interviews, obtain information on the issuer's strategic orientation.

One part of the business risk analysis is made by an evaluation of the market risk. Here it is considered the market structure and the future market development. Another part of the business analysis consists of the study of the strategic risk. The first thing is to estimate the issuer strategic position, taking in account the expected market development and the key factor to success. Consequently, at this step of investigation there is an implementation of the requirements to adequate resources, competencies and adaptability to structural changes.

After all these evaluations, the business risk is assigned to one of five categories based on the weight.

Financial risk analysis is done on the applicable audit report for the past three to five years including the segment report. Earnings power, capital structure and the cash flow/financial flexibility are the main voices in the financial study. At this stage too, there is an interpretation step in which are weighted, in six categories, the financial analysis and the financial planning.

Using a matrix, in particular the “EHR rating matrix”, business risk and financial risk are condensed together to obtain a sub-rating. This process is named Anchor rating.

However, at this point operational risks or external factors coming from possible group or public sector membership are not considered. To overcome this fact, the following “stand-alone” rating evaluates, separately from business and financial risk, the internal structures and processes of an organization. The rating assigned to the issuer in question results as the output “modification 1” (see Figure 10).

Taking into consideration the influence of the background group or the public sector background of a rated company, the stand-alone rating undergoes a “modification 2” step, that produces the final issuer rating for the company, defining the issuer’s final credit rating (see also Figure 10).

Figure 10: Derivation of issuer rating (courtesy of TRIBRating)

Issue rating methodology

The issue rating is based on the issuer rating. While the latter is a general estimation of the creditworthiness of a company, the former focus on the contractual and structural elements of an issue. The issue rating expresses the agency's evaluation of the probability of default and the loss given default of a specific financial instrument.

The issue rating methodology is structured into two analytic fields: issue terms/creditor protection rights, and recovery rate.

The creditor protection rights are assessed following four categories, that in their turn contain different points of evaluation:

1. Key financial ration/financial covenants
2. Termination rights
3. Negative pledges/ declarations of undertaking
4. Personal undertakings

On the other side, the recovery rate is calculated with the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Recovery rate} \\
 & = \\
 & \frac{(\text{value of the assets less the collateral provided for the issue} - \text{senior liabilities})}{(\text{issue liabilities} + \text{liabilities with the same ranking})} \\
 & + \\
 & \left(\frac{\text{value of the collateral granted for the issue}}{\text{issue liabilities}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

After all these evaluations, a notching table is realized, and it expresses the view of the relative credit quality of financial instrument in the company's capital structure. It is based on the following formula:

$$\text{Expected loss} = \text{Probability of default} * \text{Loss given}$$

The final result indicates the knowledge (in notches) on which the issuer rating should be adapted to arrive at the issue rating.

Figure 11: Notching table that indicates the extent to which the issuer rating must be adjusted to arrive at the issue rating

		Quality of the issue terms		
		Extensive creditor protection	Reasonable creditor protection	Inadequate creditor protection
Recovery rate	90% - 100%	+3	+2 / +3*	0 / +2*
	70% - 90%	+2	+1 / +2*	0 / +1*
	50% - 70%	+1	0 / +1*	-1 / 0*
	30% - 50%	0	-1	-2
	10% - 30%	-1	-2	-3
	0% - 10%	-2	-3	-3

4.3 Ernst & Young – EY Startup radar

Ernst & Young has developed a methodology for the scouting of innovative solutions, which aims to lead to business growth. The Innovation Strategy Technology Radar leverages on EY international offices operating within local innovation ecosystems. EY works in conjunction with top global Universities, Research Centers and Startup Hubs, in order to act as a global new business accelerator.

Figure 12: EY international offices operating within local innovation ecosystems

Once all the possible valuable information is gathered, the focus is on clearly understanding the firm's need, defining its strategic and technological challenges and, in particular, the area of improvement. To do this, the company can use tools such as surveys, cross department interview, meeting with R&D department to have an overview of the current situation. Then, it has to look on the external environment and understand in which area it might find some solutions pertinent to its goal.

This led to structure a series of superimposed layers. Layer 3 allows to build a strategic framework on which to execute the radar. Firm's strategic paradigm as well as desired objectives are leveraged in order to devise the perfect fit. Layer 2 involves the rationalization of objectives and the communication to the ecosystem of the firm's desired initiatives. The result is a relevant influx of ideas and startups that can be screened using a structured funnel. Layer 1 involves the shortlisting and decision on behalf of the firm of the most interesting decisions in order to set up deep dive interviews and find synergies.

Figure 13: Generic structure of EY Startup radar's methodology

It is possible to identify three different levels of approach according to the need's depth.

The first and most basic level is the one driven by company's technological needs, related to the company core business, and that responds to the need of an external look for innovations at the core processes of the company. The next more complex level is called adjacency innovation, which is oriented to integrate an existing business, processes and activities with adjacent technologies to reach new business opportunities. The last and most in-depth level is the strategic one, that comprehends the opportunities to work on business development or exploring new market and products.

Figure 14: Structured funnel for Startups screening

Focusing mainly on the most complex one, the strategic innovation approach is refined by a 5 steps process to find the best match for a company's needs. The first step involves meeting with the firm to define the research parameters, analyzing internal and external gaps, as well as cross-functional meetings to align the organization on the strategic direction to be taken. The second step is the analysis of data collected: quantitative analysis and scoring to evaluate the impact of the innovation

within the perimeters defined in the previous step and to correlate the results with the market trends. The next phase is scouting, in which the company has to find different innovations that could response to the previously cited needs. There are two different typologies of approach: the Induction approach sees the use of dedicated contest, like “Call4idea” or “Hackathon”, committed both to the internal and external environment; the Proactive approach, instead, has companies to search by their own possible innovations in the outside environment. An identification of approx. 1.000 fitting startups based on the similarity score and the research parameters is obtained. Then, a preliminary screening of the startups is performed based on the available data, in order to achieve a “most fitting short-list” (approx. 150). The fourth step involves due diligence and negotiation, a deep analysis focusing on technical details and legal aspects with the aim to reduce the list of solution. This is performed through a qualitative evaluation via interviews, financial analysis, meeting with experts on the technology involved, etc. The result of approx. 15 startups will be presented to the client and negotiation step begins. The last step sees the presentation to the firm of the collaboration opportunities identified, followed by the identification of the most adapted modalities to collaborate with possible startups (i.e. VC, M&A, JV, etc.).

To achieve an efficient matchmaking, a structured model of qualitative and quantitative analysis is implemented. This method is based on drivers and KPIs such as:

- Accessibility – quantifies the gap between the emerging technology solution and the feasibility of its implementation in light of the economic and business environments;
- Potential – quantification of the potential economic and social impact in case of implementation of the technological solution;
- Dynamism – quantification of the amount of capital that moves technology in both quantitative and qualitative.

Figure 15 shows the breakdown of the different factors, each rated from 1 to 5, that lead to an overall 0-100% score based on the average score.

Figure 15: EY Startup radar, quantitative evaluation breakdown

In order to screen the scouting process output, before due diligence, meetings, etc., each startup is mapped based on its perceived quality and fit following the quantitative and qualitative analysis. This

graph serves as a means of positioning each initiative, helping the firm in selecting the most suitable solution to move forwards in the radar process.

Figure 16: Mapping of selected Startups to help identifying the most suitable ones

4.4 Early Metrics – Early Metrics’ rating model

Early Metrics has developed a precise rating model for business decision makers in order to identify the most innovative and high-tech startup for collaboration. The company works to simplify the dialogue of companies with the complex startup ecosystem, helps partners creating innovation programs and investments supporting by active collaboration, information and decision-making processes.

The solution offered by Early Metrics starts from three main categories that are: discovery, qualification and engagement.

Regarding discovery, evaluating what startups are doing and what they are working on can be useful to identify some of the problems that are affecting a certain market. Assessment of startup’s ecosystem, creation of precise market reports and providing of detailed key trend solutions, are the principles duty of the discovery phase. There is a *high growth index*, which is a high-level assessment and ranking of startups across the company client network, focusing on growth capacity. Based on non-publicly information, the index supports quick analysis and monitoring performance. Another service at this stage is the *startup ecosystem mapping*, that provides a deep understanding of specific macro evolutions associated with selected technologies and markets. Focus on how agile/smart companies work to create innovative products and services

Moving towards the next step of Early Metrics solutions, the aim is the collaboration with startups. Collaboration could be an effective way to overcome the obstacles restricting innovation development across various markets around the world. With the previous purpose, Early Metrics works finding and rating relevant startups, using their extensive network to create functional links, and presenting the most qualified startups to their client. The *qualified sourcing* is a constant submission of qualified

startups, based on predefined set of criteria like market, maturity and location. Sharing of deep expertise and network in startups and innovative SMEs to identify the one that could be value adding partners to the company's innovative initiatives. Every month is presented a research over different interesting startup that could be potentially suitable for Early Metrics 'client.

One of the final stages that a startup has to face is an engagement evaluation in which are assessed key parameter for success. *Rating on demand* can be done through:

- *Small co-development: Check* – high level overview of startup ranking analysis powered by scientifically-backed methodology, including strengths and weaknesses.
- *Long term collaboration: Deep check* – in depth analysis providing a comprehensive assessment of start-up growth potential along 3 pillars: people (founder skills and expertise, teamwork and compatibility, management competences, etc.); project (product development roadmap, product technical maturity, level of innovation, etc.); market (addressable market size, external pressures on profit, terms of competitiveness, etc.).
- *Minority stage investment: Scan* – pre-deal commercial due diligence on start-up, composed of Deep-Check plus an independent financial assessment.

Another service provided by Early Metrics is the *innovation workshop*, that can be translated in:

- *Upstream Workshop: design and structure impactful programs* – identify innovation topics requiring the majority of attention and re-elaborate these into realizable and impactful programs.
- *Downstream workshop: choose best startup based on compatibility* – manage and host pitch days on behalf of clients in order to showcase innovative solutions being developed by startups to wider members of the business.

Figure 17: Scheme of Early Metrics’ assessment iter (courtesy of Early Metrics)

4.5 Skopai – Innovation intelligence platform

Skopai has developed a platform that gives objective information on any startup in the world. The objective is to build an AI-based platform for tech in order to provide real-time, complete information of any startup anywhere in the world. The platform uses the state-of-the-art AI algorithms to detect, monitor and analyze startups and, then, qualify them. To accomplish this task, Skopai collects and aggregates data from the web (startup websites, newsletter, social networks, etc.). After this passage, data are processed to infer information about startups. The approach uses a wide variety of algorithms ranging from simple rules to sophisticated machine learning techniques. To train and evaluate the models, innovation experts continually work with the R&D scientists.

To assess a startup or a SME, Skopai offers an investigation that is mainly organized in four categories:

The first is the *inferred* information: starting from the point that financial or commercial information on innovative SME and startup are not promptly available, these types of details must be inferred from the latest knowledge accessible and evaluate through the evolution over time.

The second category is the *360-degree information*: startup are companies that are growing. For this reason, any evaluation on them should consider all the dimensions of the business. Fundraising or media footprints are usual metrics, on the other side reflecting on product, technology, market, customers, team skills or partnership gives the opportunity to see the whole picture.

Then there are *objective and standardized information*: The Startup analysis is based on the context and the preparation of the person performing it. It is for this purpose that the information collected from the platform need to be non-biased, objective and standardized.

Finally, *real-time information*: an obvious consequence of the rapidity of evolution of startups is the need of real-time information monitoring.

Data Sciences and Artificial Intelligence are the technologies at the basis of the platform. All the knowledge collected and stored is than guaranteed by world-class innovation experts.

4.6 Clarivate Analytics – Derwent

In the realization of the “Derwent top 100 global innovators”, Derwent (an application of Clarivate Analytics) starts from a patent landscape analysis. Beginning with this approach, in the following lines will be explained how Derwent manages to implement different analysis.

Patents are considered as a strategic value of innovation. Governments, academia and industry use them to inform policy decisions, track trends and collect technological and commercial intelligence. Clearly a direct counting of granted patents is useful, but it only represents a part of a bigger and more relevant vision. In order to exploit the whole potential of a patent, what is measured is not only the volume of inventions, but also the patent quality, globalization and impact.

The *Derwent solutions* system includes *Derwent World Patents Index (DWPI)*, *Derwent Innovation* and the *Derwent Patent Citations Index (DPCI)*. Thanks to this methodology it is possible to analyze patent portfolio strength and quality by organization, evaluating not just a huge number of archived patents, but success in obtaining granted patents, a rich filing of invention and external citations.

The analysis is accomplished through four steps:

Volume: analysis of all organization with 100 or more patented new inventions covered by a granted patent in the last 5 years. A new invention is defined as the publication of a patent document claiming a technology, drug, process or other, not previously described as prior art. In DWPI, these are called “basics”. DWPI provides a record of patents published by 50 patent issuing authorities worldwide to provide a whole landscape. Files for the same invention are called “equivalents” and collected in “patent families”. Once an organization passes through this selection, it is assessed across the following steps.

Success: from the presupposition that not all the analyzed patents will become granted patents, the Success metric evaluate the quality of innovation focusing on the ratio over the most recent five years of inventions described in published applications to inventions protected with granted patents.

Globalization: the number of basic inventions that have quadrilateral patents in their patent families, according to the DWPI, is calculated to create a ratio that shows which companies place a high value on their portfolios in major world markets

Influence: using *Derwent Patents Citation Index*, citations of an organization’s patents were counted over the last five years, self-citations are not considered. The impact of an innovation transferability is assessed looking at how often it is subsequently cited by other companies in the patenting of their innovation.

These criteria create a combined indicator score that Derwent used to identify the top 100 most innovative organizations globally.

4.7 Startup Ranking – Startup Ranking’s platform

An approach that shows a progressive growth in the evaluation of a new startup is based on the social metrics strategy. “Startup Ranking” is a platform in which every startup registered is placed in a specific position. The whole process is organized around a “SR Score”, this is simply a number between 0 and 100.000. The SR Score is so important because it reflects the importance of the startup on the internet and its social influence. These two parameters are calculated based on “SR web” and “SR social”.

SR web

It is also a number between 0 and 100.000, which reflects the importance of a startup on the internet. In order to do this the “Startup ranking” team has evaluated different factors, and an explicative bunch of them is shown below:

- Number and quality of web pages that link to a startup web page. The higher the quality of the incoming links, the higher the SR Web.
- Distribution of internal links – links that point to other pages in the same domain. The better the distribution of internal links, the higher the SR Web.
- Number and quality of external links – links from a startup web page that point to an external web page. The higher the quality of external links, the higher the SR Web.
- On-Page SEO (search engine optimization) factors such as:
 - Content of a page: The content should be related to the startup and the page title.
 - Title Tag: The title element of a startup web page is meant to be an accurate and concise description of a page's content.
 - URL: The URL of a startup web page is meant to be an accurate and concise description of a page's content.
- Estimated audience factors:
 - Number of estimated visits and unique visitors to the startup web site.
 - Number of estimated pageviews and pageviews per visit to the startup web site.
 - Estimated average of visit duration.

The higher the number of these factors, the higher the SR Web.

SR social

Another range of numbers between 0 and 100.000, this score reflects the social influence of the startup.

The factors taken into account are:

- Facebook engagement:
 - Number of likes for the fan page.
 - Number of likes for posts.
 - Number of comments for posts.
 - Number of shares for posts.
 - Number of persons engaged with the fan page.
- Twitter engagement:
 - Number of followers.
 - Number and quality of retweets.

- Number of favorites for tweets.
- Number of persons engaged with the account.

The higher the number of these factors, the higher the SR Social.

SR Web and SR Social are inputs to the SR Score algorithm and the resulting number is shown on the precise Startup Profile. The key feature of this type of method of evaluation is based on the social and internet spreading of a startup. Talking about startups nowadays is strictly linked to innovation. From this point of view, a ranking of this type could be a support system of assessment of investments on SMEs and startup in addition to the most classical ones. With this interpretation it is possible to reach fields of analysis not reachable with the financials or the more traditional ones, social metrics methods could be complementary to them in order to realize a 360 degrees study.

4.8 Italian Space Agency – PoInMeS

The idea of developing a system providing an innovative technology assessment could be realized through the use of predictive intelligence and semantic implemented methods. It's around this concept that the Italian Space Agency worked on PoInMeS. This has been developed as a tool for innovative technology observation to map the main space technology in a national and international landscape.

A predictive analysis uses different techniques from data mining, statistics, modeling, machine learning and artificial intelligence in order to evaluate current data to make predictions about the future. Recognizing the relationships among many factors, it is possible to assess different conditions and from them assign a score. Such type of process applied to investors or business world is by itself representative of its potential.

The enormous amount of data needed by these processes can be categorized in:

- structured (e.g. income, sales, age, gender etc.)
- unstructured (e.g. textual data in social media content, general open text files, etc.)

For the collection and the first step of data assessment, PoInMeS uses a semantic analysis technique, that can potentially cover a vast and heterogeneous field of interests. The idea of mapping different key words group can clean and filter the collected information.

Then, a complementary approach is applied to delineate the outer and the inner environment of the previous conclusions. The "Nine box analysis", investigating both temporal and spatial dimensions of the technology, returns cause-effect ratio and fields of possible application. In particular it considers the technology past history, current state-of-play, and future potential, and on the other hand the super system, the system itself, and the subsystem.

Implementing approaches like TRIZ (inventing problem solving) is also an additional force that leads to obtain additional knowledge. This method has different applications in various sceneries, and it aims is to subdivide a main problem in smaller and simplified sub-classes, easier to be evaluated and solved.

At this point, the technology has been broken down to a series of relevant keywords, and a statistical analysis on all the data collected can be performed. Data collected in this way could be patents landscape, published articles, technologies actual usage, social metrics parameters, etc.

The adding value brought from semantic analysis is actually the magnitude of resources investigated. This helps to highlight trends, most important players in the market, network nodes, and the direction of the segment analyzed.

Nonetheless, the team at the base of the method suggests a parallel validation with experts. These can be listened by fiscal consulting or by using online recruitment session, in which a much larger number of specialized experts can share their knowledge.

Semantic and predictive intelligence analysis tools, with the support of experts, could results in a reliable starting point.

4.9 Cross matrix technique

Despite the development of technology rating models, technology-based rating models can cause high potential risk of default if they do not consider financial aspects that have direct impacts on default. In addition, most private banks and investors have the tendency to give more credit to companies that have high financial strength or sufficient security, rather than those with innovative technology, because they are mainly concerned about the retrieval of loans. Therefore, both technology-related attributes and financial aspects should be considered in a rating model for technology evaluation, and there is the need to combine the two together. In this paragraph, a method to combine technology and financial evaluation is presented, even if it is not currently used.

A research from Yonsei University in Seoul (ROK) proposed a technology credit rating system, called cross matrix (Moon et al., 2010), which improves existing methods that apply a simple average or weighted average of two evaluation results having different characteristics. The results from the two models can be tabulated in a two-dimensional matrix according to their technology and finance scores, respectively. Typically, a linear combination approach would combine two different scores in an indistinguishable manner, however, for a flexible and effective implementation, combining them considering the different aspects of the two scoring models results to be more effective. Thus, the new cross matrix technique has been proposed.

A cross matrix makes it possible to set up rating criteria using a combination of default rate of technology scores and finance scores, respectively, in a two-dimensional matrix. A default rate is calculated as the proportion of the number of defaults in a cell to the total number of companies. As a result, the default rate of each combination of technology and finance scores is obtained. Then, the cross-matrix technique flexibly assigns ratings to intersections considering the default rate of each rating. The rating assignment based on the cross-default rate can be flexibly implemented according to the organization's strategy and policy on the risk management. In other words, the cross matrix can be constructed adaptively without any limit, according, to the purpose and peculiarities of the technology evaluation policy. To incentivize SMEs with promising technology, higher ratings can be assigned to companies with high technology scores and low finance scores than to those with low technology scores and high finance scores. In addition, a cross matrix can be used as a filter by setting a threshold value for the finance score so that companies that do not satisfy the criterion, even if they have a high technology score, can be excluded. Finally, since each rating involves both technological and financial levels, it is possible to develop differentiated strategies for different ratings.

In Table 1 the results from the study are presented, showing the default rate comparison between the proposed technology rating system based on the cross matrix (that had been applied since 2005), the previous technology rating system (used from 1999 to 2004) and finally a credit rating system based on financial metrics. As it can be seen, the overall default rate of the technology rating system

substantially decreased from 3.28% to 0.47%, which is also lower than the overall default rate of the credit rating system (1.00%).

Table 1: Default rate comparison of different rating system (Moon et al., 2011)

Rating	New technology rating system			Previous technology rating system			Credit rating system		
	# firms	# defaults	Default rate (%)	# firms	# defaults	Default rate (%)	# firms	# defaults	Default rate (%)
AAA	3	0	0.00	—	—	—	283	—	0.00
AA	61	0	0.00	18	0	0.00	178	4	2.25
A	388	3	0.77	630	20	3.17	263	4	1.52
BBB	926	3	0.32	2757	99	3.59	934	10	1.07
BB	1325	5	0.38	1361	51	3.75	786	7	0.89
B	1614	8	0.50	484	8	1.65	861	10	1.16
CCC	340	3	0.88	247	2	0.81	1,038	7	0.67
CC	2	0	0.00	24	1	4.17	235	2	0.85
C	—	—	—	2	0	0.00	18	2	11.11
Total	4659	22	0.47	5523	181	3.28	4596	46	1.00

5. Challenges and gaps

Here, an overall analysis of the pros and cons of the different methodologies is presented, along with challenges and gaps that are still present and that are to be solved by InnoRate project.

In the tables presented below, the different types of evaluation, approaches and the tools used by the various companies are summed and grouped. For each one of them, the valuable aspects as well as the negative ones are presented, in order to highlight the key features of every voice.

Table 2: Pros and cons of different types of evaluation

Type of evaluation	✓ Pros	✗ Cons
Financial evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Essential for investors ○ Needed for a correct assessment of default risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Could underestimate potentially disruptive innovations
Technology evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Good evaluation for potentially disruptive innovations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Could underestimate default risk

Table 3: Pros and cons of different approaches

Approaches	✓ Pros	✗ Cons
Qualitative approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Captures softer aspects ○ Leverages experience ○ Provides background insights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Requires skills and experience ○ Subjectivity
Quantitative approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hard data and numerical clarification ○ Easy-to-compare results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Could miss useful insights

Table 4: Pros and cons of different tools

Tools	✓ Pros	✗ Cons
Interviews with experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Value of experts' knowledge and experience ○ Access to private company's information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Subjectivity ○ Not suited for big number of evaluations
Mathematical models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Powerful tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Diversity of project types, resources and criteria used
Scoring models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Simplicity ○ Robustness ○ Can be back tested 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Often require expert's knowledge and experience
Rating models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Easy to identify ○ Diversification of strategies ○ Easy to compare ○ Used by financial institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Rating categories must be defined properly
Predictive Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Magnitude of resources investigated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Large sample size required ○ Credibility of performance criteria
AI implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Objectivity of the process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ "Black box approach" ○ Overgeneralization
Patent landscape analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Evaluation of IP's value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Need for a credible IP valuation approach
Social metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Useful insight into social success 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Need to be correctly evaluated
Cross matrix technique	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flexibility ○ Can serve as a threshold filter ○ Differentiated strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Weights used should be specified

In general, looking at the main characteristics that distinguish one methodology from another, a schematic representation can group the existing evaluation tools in four major areas (see Figure 18).

Traditional bank’s rating tools for large corporates fill the area corresponding to financial evaluation conducted via qualitative internal assessment. Moving to financial evaluation with a quantitative approach, apart from the big financial rating companies such as Standard and Poor’s Corporation, Moody’s and Fitch Rating, TRIBRating emerge as a complete service particularly suited for SMEs. Then, several companies perform technological evaluation, qualitatively or quantitatively (such as Jolt Capital’s Ninja platform, which aims at faster identifying interesting European high-tech companies).

Some companies, however, are conducting both a financial and a technological evaluation, putting together the results obtained separately. EY Startup radar for example integrates a quantitative method to map the best firms and a qualitative approach fulfilled by a team of experts.

KOTEC technology rating system stands out as the most structured quantitative tech assessment tool, integrating a technology score with a risk score.

Figure 18: Schematic representation of existing evaluation tools

Finally, some additional features, particularly grown in recent years due to big data analysis and tools development, seem to be extremely interesting to implement as a tool for improving technology assessment. For instance, patent landscape analysis, a multistep process that aims at extracting value from IP information, enabling investors and lenders to better understand and make informed decision before investing into new technology opportunities.

In parallel, AI is proving to be an extremely powerful tool for analyzing the big amount of data that are accessible nowadays, extracting useful information in short amount of time. More and more companies are starting to leverage the potential of this tool.

Based also on big data analysis, predictive intelligence makes predictions on emerging trends, market shifts, market’s player, etc.

One last feature that is recently emerging regards the use and evaluation of social metrics, through which it is possible to obtain useful insights into the success of a technology or a firm, and so it's potential growth. These metrics reflect the importance on the internet and the influence of the firm.

Figure 19: Overview of interesting additional tools

6. Preliminary evaluation of InnoRate's ideas

This section presents the event “Innovation Talks”, organized by Unismart in collaboration with the University of Padua, that took place on the 18th of March 2019.

The event, attended by more than 300 people (entrepreneurs, investors and innovators), was held in *Sala dei Giganti* in Padua, Italy. This great hall (literally “Hall of the Giants”) was named from the size of the figures depicted in the frescoes, all personages of Ancient Rome. The main theme of the event was technology transfer, and how innovation in general is and could be assessed. The last of the three panels covered a comparison between different technology transfer models, and how to best evaluate innovation opportunities. Being one of the panelists, Unismart presented the InnoRate project and its objective to encourage innovation through a structured assessment methodology.

A questionnaire was provided to all participants (see Appendix 3), in order to further spread awareness about the project and to gather useful insights, since the audience was composed by relevant stakeholders. Since the questionnaire was to be completed during the event, to not steal too much time to the participants and to increase the likelihood of compilation, the number of questions had been kept low, and rather than structuring it with open questions, a closed form had been used.

A significant statistical analysis was not possible, but nonetheless some considerations emerged. For example, the majority of the stakeholders not only doesn't apply a technology assessment tool, but often doesn't even know any. Nonetheless, especially when talking about high-tech companies, the relevance of technology/patent potential is taken in high consideration, sometimes even more than the financial aspects. This supports the idea that there is a strong need of a structured and consistent technology assessment methodology, to fill this grey area. Another confirmation that emerged is that the most used and familiar rating methodology involves a quantitative analysis, resulting in a final score or rating. However, the score itself seems not to be enough, since investors expressed also the necessity to be provided with information and data in order to then make their own evaluation. Finally, it has been investigated their perception about the importance of "social metrics" (e.g. followers, leads per post, etc.), but in this case there is not a clear result, and it seems that there is not yet sufficient awareness about them.

7. Conclusions

From the wide research and analysis of the different existing technology assessment methodologies, tools and services that has been conducted, several results can be drawn. First of all, technology evaluation approaches can be categorized looking at two main aspects: what they evaluate and how they evaluate.

Regarding what they evaluate, the distinction is between approaches that focus on evaluating financial aspects and past history of the company, essentially measuring its default risk, rather than approaches that try to evaluate the technology's disruptive and future potential. This in general comprehends four major categories: the technology itself, the management capability, the marketability of the technology, and the business feasibility.

Both financial and technological aspects proved to be essential for a correct technology evaluation. The former cannot be excluded in order to adequately estimate the company's default risk and not underestimate it. The latter instead is the key to properly assess the future growth potential of the technology. Also, from preliminary insights obtained from interviews conducted during the study and through the questionnaires gathered at the "Innovation Talks" event, investors too seem to value positively a way to better grasp the technological aspect of innovative companies.

On the other side, technology assessment methodologies can be distinguished also depending on how they perform the evaluation, i.e. if through qualitative interviews with experts or producing a quantitative result applying complex mathematical models or scorecards with different factors.

The most used and successful assessment method has proved to be constituted by multi-dimensional scoring sheets and rating processes. In fact, in addition to their simplicity and robustness, they are easy to interpret and different strategies can be developed for each different rating.

Nonetheless, evaluation of experts leveraging on their experience and perceptions seems to be a factor that cannot be excluded. Furthermore, again from the preliminary insights gathered, many investors and lenders tend to require and prefer to have also access to direct data and information about the company in order to make their own evaluation.

From this study, some additional interesting features emerged too, such as patent landscape analysis, implementation of predictive and artificial intelligence for big data analysis, and social metrics. It could be worth to further investigate them and potentially integrate in the new assessment tool.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 – Overview of the analyzed rating companies

Company or method	Key features	Description	Web site
Big Data Value Association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BDVA is the private counterpart to the EU Commission to implement the Big Data Value PPP program. BDVA and the Big Data Value PPP pursue a common shared vision of positioning Europe as the world leader in the creation of Big Data Value The mission of the BDVA is to develop the Innovation Ecosystem that will enable the data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe delivering maximum economic and societal benefit, and, achieving and sustaining Europe's leadership on Big Data Value creation and Artificial Intelligence 	http://www.bdva.eu/SRIA
CARE Rating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Credit rating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indian credit risk rating in comparison with other SMEs 	http://www.careratings.com/
CB insight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Predictive intelligence Language processing Graphic visualization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CB Insights Mosaic scores, created in partnership with the National Science Foundation Provides early predictive intelligence into emerging company health and momentum 	https://www.cbinsights.com/
CDI Labs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connect Startups and Big Industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building commercial relationships between the best European Startups and Big Industry. Exploration: identification and analysis of innovation themes with Industrial Partners. Selection: top European Startups selected from Excellence Network. Matching: Startups and Corporate Executives meet-up and search for proper matching. 	http://cdilabs.eu/

Company or method	Key features	Description	Web site
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot: trialing of Startups inside the Industry with the right settings to help initiate partnerships. 	
<p>Center of Excellence of FinTech program</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indian program which seems very similar to InnoRate (still in a preliminary phase) 	https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/experts-propose-rating-system-for-startups-at-city-workshop/articleshow/67494899.cms
<p>CPA Global</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Firm global leader in management of technology and IP Innovation software for the administration of PI portfolio, services and information integrated for the entire life cycle of an idea 	https://www.cpaglobal.com/it/home
<p>Cross Matrix</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial and Technology rating Flexibility Useful filter Differentiation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Successfully implemented since 2005 Improves existing methods that apply a simple average or weighted average of two evaluation results Finance score together with technology score Can be constructed adaptively according to the purpose and peculiarities of the technology evaluation policy A threshold can be set on the finance score Each rating summarizes the technology and the financial level => different strategies for different ratings 	https://www.jstor.org/stable/41059119?seq=1&cid=pdf-reference#page_scan_tab_contents
<p>Dealroom</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of tags Smart search tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helps professional investors, corporates and local governments to discover and track innovative tech companies 	https://dealroom.co/

Company or method	Key features	Description	Web site
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart search module that combines tags and filters like: location, business model, funding, industries, growth metrics and more • Market explorer to evaluate trends in whole countries, industries and around certain trending topics like AI or fintech. • Heat-maps show macro developments over time, allowing zooming into specific company & investor profiles 	
Derwent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent landscape 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides innovators with insights they can trust • More than 100 years of scientific research insights • Helps Brand Protection Managers, Paralegals, Patent Attorneys and others design and protect their brands and intellectual assets globally • Provides solutions by leveraging the world's first and most comprehensive intellectual asset management platform • Connects you to communities of insightful experts and networks to maximize the returns on your innovation investments • Patent analytics to measure innovation • TOP 100 rating list 	https://clarivate.com/products/derwent-innovation/
Early Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Startup 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Startups evaluation via extensive interviews and property method 	http://earlymetrics.com/
EY Innovation Strategy Technology Radar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Startup • Quantitative + qualitative • Comparison graphics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research on a global scale • Quantitative methods to map the best possible solutions (accessibility, potential, dynamism) • Qualitative approach fulfilled by a team of experts • Not a simple matchmaking, also a strategic consulting service • Graph to position different startups 	Material shared by EY

Company or method	Key features	Description	Web site
Finquest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big data • Machine learning • Team of experts • Confidentiality • Security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connects the global investment community and mid-sized companies across Asia-Pacific and Europe and North America. • Client's info is entered in the platform. • Finquest generates a list of potential matches using a combination of big data, machine learning and an in-house team of experts. The team refines the list and reaches out to potential connections. After agreement, the introduction is made via the Finquest platform. • More than 150 data sources and feeds. • Structured and non-structured information, Client profiling, Company information, Web crawlers, Market environment, Detailed organization profile, Industry focus, strategy and goals, Member's behavior, on Finquest and on social media. 	https://finquest.com/en/
Invention evaluator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological overview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detailed overview of the technical merit, IP position, market Landscape of an innovation • Experts' evaluation • Use of an algorithm 	https://www.inventionevaluator.com/site/
IP Score	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool for patent and research evaluation • Customizable assessment factors 	https://www.epo.org/searching-for-patents/business/ipscore.html#tab-1
Know Made	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent analysis • Tech intelligence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering them a deep understanding of their IP environment and technology trends • Prior art search, patent landscape analysis, patent valuation, IP due diligence, and freedom-to-operate analysis 	http://www.knowmade.com/

Company or method	Key features	Description	Web site
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Powerful analytics tools and proprietary methodologies to deliver relevant patent analyses and scientific reviews 	
KOTEC / KTRS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology innovation Risk evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guarantee scheme thought to help innovative SMEs whose access to credit is limited due to lack of collateral capacity, despite their prominent technological competency. 	Material shared by KOTEC
KTH Innovation Readiness Level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graphic tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Methodology, visual tool, and resource library guiding the development from early stage idea to innovation on the market 6 key areas evaluated from 1-9: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Customer Team Business IPR Funding Technology 	https://kthinno.vationreadines.slevel.com/
NGP Capital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support system of funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Founded in 2005 A support system of funding, feet on the ground in the world's largest markets, deep thematic expertise and access to vast networks as well as a technology corporate Believe growth-stage companies deserve long-term, loyal investors that have both the ambition and the discipline to create significant financial and strategic value 	https://www.ngpcap.com/
Ninja platform (Jolt Capital)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global score Patent landscape Investments criteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A platform (Ninja) aiming at faster identifying interesting European high-tech companies Criteria are: number of employees, number of patents, country, level of revenue and profitability, when available, and industry Rates companies by giving different weights on each criterion, leading to a global score for each company This rating is subjective as it matches investment criteria 	Material sent by Jolt Capital

Company or method	Key features	Description	Web site
Oddup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Startup Rating System Graphic tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical information on Startups, "Startup Rating System" 	https://www.oddup.com/
PoInMeS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Semantic analysis Predictive intelligence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ASI platform Assessment of technology innovation 	Material shared by ASI
Skopai	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Startup Data Sciences AI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Searches the web in real-time for startup information A reference platform for tech, providing real-time and complete knowledge of startups worldwide Leverages Data Sciences and Artificial Intelligence to collect, aggregate and analyze web data 	https://www.skopai.com/
Startup Ranking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Startup Non-financial metrics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SR Score (0-100) reflects the importance of a startup on the internet Based on SR Web and SR Social 	https://www.startupranking.com/
Tech Advance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tech assessment Customizable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Model with 3 axes: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Market attractiveness Technology potential People Provides an assessment method backed and validated by research Flexible to different needs as the model allows customization 	https://www.techadvance-online.com/
Toolip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patent evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patent research evaluation Patent risk and opportunity 	http://www.toolipvaluation.com/
TRIBRating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Credit rating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launched in Germany in June 2017, TRIBRating recognizes, analyzes and monitors the specific credit characteristics of SMEs and MidCaps, provided by Euler Hermes Rating GmbH Enabling smaller businesses to gain a transparent and internationally comparable credit rating using the well-known AAA to D full spectrum global scale 	https://www.ehrg.de/en/tribrating/

Company or method	Key features	Description	Web site
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uniform rating, and consistent across different sectors 	
<p>URSIT (Uniform Rating System for Information Technology)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology rating system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on risk evaluation of 4 critical components: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Audit Management Development and Acquisition Support and Delivery Used since 1978 	<p>https://ithandbook.ffiec.gov/it-booklets/supervision-of-technology-service-providers/risk-based-supervision/uniform-rating-system-for-information-technology.aspx</p>

Appendix 2 – Questionnaire provided on the “Innovation Talks” event on 18th of March

InnoRate project “Data-driven tools for supporting and improving the decision-making processes of investors for financing innovative SMEs” is a project financed by the European Commission in the context of H2020, and its objective is to develop a platform for the assessment of high-tech companies and their intangibles assets.

Survey addressed to stakeholders specialized in technology innovation

1. Category of belonging:

- Investor (Bank, VC, etc.) Intermediary (Accelerator, Incubator, Broker, etc.)
 “Innovator” (Big enterprise, PMI, Startup, etc.)

2. Do you know/use methods or tools to assess high-tech company or new technologies?

- Yes, I frequently use them Yes, but I rarely use them
 Yes, but I don’t use them No, I don’t know any of them

3. How do you define the methodology that you mainly use?

- Qualitative (experts’ analysis) Quantitative (score, rating) Other _____

4. Barriers/obstacles/lacks that you have encountered? _____

5. Do you consider more important in a high-tech company assessment the financials/tangibles aspects, the technologies/intangibles ones or a well-balanced mix of the previous?

- Mainly the financial aspects Mainly the technologies/patents potential
 Both aspects with the same importance

6. Would you promote a rating system of high-tech companies that considers also “social” metrics, i.e. web reputation (e.g. followers, leads per post, etc.)?

- Yes No I don’t know

7. Would you trust a rating given by an automatic system, able to elaborate big quantities of data to compare a firm and its assets with similar or potentially comparable cases, or do you prefer a system providing you a base of selected data, in order to perform an assessment with your own criteria or with experts’ involvement?

- Yes, I would trust it No, I would just want additional information Both of them

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